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Perceived adolescent insecure attachment with mothers and fathers: links with food addiction, eating disorders, and weight status

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to test relationships between adolescent insecure attachment (anxious and avoidant) with mothers and fathers and three outcomes: food addiction, eating disorders, and weight status, in a large multi-regional sample of Czech adolescents. Anonymous, self-reported data were collected from 3,677 adolescents (1,688 boys, 45.9% and 1,989 girls, 54.1%). Both anxious and avoidant attachment with mothers were positively associated with food addiction ($p < .001$) and eating-disorder risk ($p < .001$). Importantly, avoidant attachment with fathers uniquely and additively explained variance in both food addiction ($p < .001$) and eating-disorder risk ($p = .003$), after controlling for maternal attachment. Weight status was unrelated to attachment and was predicted by sex and parental education only. Study findings highlight the salience of insecure attachment with both mothers and fathers for food addiction and eating disorders among adolescents and identify the parental relationship as a key potential preventative strategy.

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Obesity; overweight; attachment; food addiction; eating disorders; Czech population

Introduction

Disordered eating and food-related psychopathology are rising public health problems, with global eating-disorder prevalence doubling in the past two decades—from 3.5% (2000–2006) to 7.8% (2013–2018) (Galmiche et al., 2019). Food addiction is defined as a compulsive pattern of eating behaviour involving loss of control, cravings, and continued use despite negative consequences, modelled after diagnostic criteria for substance use disorders (Gearhardt et al., 2016). In contrast, eating disorders (EDs) such as anorexia nervosa or bulimia nervosa are classified as psychiatric conditions with well-defined criteria in the DSM-5 (American Psychiatric Association, 2013), characterized by disturbed eating behaviours and body image issues.

Adolescence is a critical developmental period during which eating-related problems often emerge, posing significant public health concerns. Recent systematic reviews confirm that food addiction (FA) is relatively common in adolescents. A 2021 meta-analysis of 52 studies reported a pooled FA prevalence of 15% among youth, including 12% in community samples and up to 19% in overweight or obese groups (Yekaninejad et al., 2021). More recent work shows similar rates across non-clinical adolescent populations, with substantially higher prevalence in dieting, clinical, or high-risk groups (Praxedes et al., 2022; Skinner et al., 2021). FA in adolescents has been linked to depressive symptoms, emotional dysregulation, and insecure attachment (Huang et al., 2022; Liese et al., 2020), consistent with earlier findings showing that attachment anxiety and avoidance are associated with compulsive or dysregulated eating addiction (Álvarez-Malé & Castaño, 2015; Bentham et al., 2017; Pipová et al., 2020).

Longitudinal and cross-sectional studies further suggest that attachment insecurity predicts eating-disorder symptoms (Illing et al., 2010) and may contribute to maladaptive eating trajectories such as binge-type behaviours or restrictive patterns (Gander, 2015). FA may also function as a mechanism linking emotional regulation difficulties with higher body mass index (BMI) in adolescence (Schiestl & Gearhardt,

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2018; Schulte et al., 2018). Together, these findings highlight the importance of relational and affective processes in understanding food-related psychopathology during adolescence. These findings underscore the need to consider relational mechanisms, particularly attachment processes, that may shape adolescents' vulnerability to food addiction and disordered eating.

Attachment theory, first introduced by John Bowlby (1982), emphasizes that early relationships with caregivers form the basis for later emotional regulation, self-esteem, and interpersonal functioning. Inconsistent or unresponsive caregiving is thought to result in insecure attachment patterns, such as heightened fear of abandonment or discomfort with closeness. Building on Bowlby's foundational work, Brennan et al. (1998) proposed a widely used model that conceptualizes attachment along two dimensions: attachment anxiety and attachment avoidance. Attachment anxiety reflects the fear of rejection and the desire for closeness, while avoidance reflects discomfort with intimacy and dependence on others. Based on these two dimensions, individuals can also be categorized into four attachment styles (Bartholomew, 1990), namely, secure, anxious/preoccupied, dismissing-avoidant, and fearful-avoidant.

A meta-analysis by Solmi et al. (2022) and a systematic review by Galmiche et al. (2019) show that most EDs begin during adolescence, with a median age of onset around 18 years and a peak onset around 15.5 years. Food-related problems and BMI are linked to mental health difficulties. Several contributing factors have been identified, including poor self-control, impulsivity, and attachment difficulties (Liese et al., 2020; Tasca et al., 2006), which are well contextualized by Bowlby's pioneering theory of attachment (1982).

Across adolescence, attachment processes shift as young people navigate increasing autonomy while still relying on their parents' emotional support. Difficulties in balancing these needs may increase vulnerability to disordered eating (Gander, 2015).

Attachment and food addiction in adolescence

Insecure attachment has been consistently associated with difficulties in emotion regulation, which may increase vulnerability to compulsive or addictive-like eating behaviours in adolescence. Attachment anxiety and avoidance have been linked to maladaptive coping strategies, including the use of food to regulate distress or compensate for unmet emotional needs (Álvarez-Malé & Castaño, 2015; Bentham et al., 2017; Pipová et al., 2020). Recent work also highlights broader psychosocial processes that contribute to food addiction. Perceived weight stigma is reliably associated with higher FA symptoms, partly through increased internalized self-stigma and psychological distress (Huang et al., 2022). Psychological distress further mediates the link between problematic social media use and FA (Huang et al., 2023), while weight stigma may directly exacerbate FA among adolescents with higher body weight (Huang et al., 2024). Together, these findings suggest that both attachment-related and psychosocial stressors contribute to the development of addictive-like eating patterns during adolescence.

Attachment and eating disorders in adolescence

A substantial body of research demonstrates that insecure attachment is a risk factor for the development and maintenance of eating disorders (Tasca et al., 2006). Both anxious and avoidant attachment styles have been implicated, with anxious attachment often associated with heightened concern about rejection and increased vulnerability to disordered eating (Klein et al., 2022; Tasca et al., 2006). Adolescents with insecure attachment frequently struggle with internal affect regulation (Lavik et al., 1991), and eating behaviours may function as maladaptive strategies for regulating distress or seeking comfort (Sharpe et al., 1998). Clinical studies have shown elevated rates of insecure attachment, fear of abandonment, and autonomy difficulties among individuals with anorexia nervosa and other eating disorders (Ramacciotti et al., 2001). A recent meta-analysis further confirmed significantly higher rates of insecure attachment among individuals with eating disorders compared to controls (Jewell et al., 2023). These findings underscore that attachment difficulties play a central role in the emotional and interpersonal mechanisms underlying eating disorder psychopathology (Tasca et al., 2006; Ward et al., 2000). More recent work highlights that insecure maternal attachment predicts depressive symptoms, which in turn are associated with disordered eating in adolescents (Cortés-García et al., 2022), further supporting the relevance of attachment-related pathways during this developmental period.

Attachment and weight status in adolescence

In a longitudinal study among adolescent girls, insecure attachment was associated with higher BMI (Milan & Acker, 2014). Attachment quality has a direct effect on self-control, impulsivity, self-efficacy of eating, and hence on obesity, highlighting the role of secure attachments in preventing childhood obesity (Bahrami et al., 2013). Thus, attachment insecurity increases the likelihood of higher BMI across all ages.

Several demographic factors, such as age, sex, and parental education, have also been linked to variability in eating behaviours and weight status among adolescents (Borisenkov et al., 2020; Cinelli et al., 2020; Naghashpour et al., 2018; Pursey et al., 2014; Skinner et al., 2021). However, these correlates are insufficient to explain why some adolescents develop food addiction or eating-disorder symptoms while others do not, as some studies report inconsistent or even opposite associations (e.g. Meule et al., 2017). This underscores the importance of considering relational mechanisms such as attachment, which may better account for individual differences in vulnerability to food addiction and disordered eating.

Socioeconomic factors such as parental education and family income have also been associated with adolescent overweight and obesity in prior research (The Health Behaviour in School-aged Children [HBSC], 2020; Grassi et al., 2016; Vignerová et al., 2006). However, these structural influences do not fully explain why adolescents differ in their eating-related psychopathology or weight status. Interpersonal mechanisms, particularly attachment quality, may offer a more developmentally meaningful framework for understanding these patterns.

Although evidence on attachment and disordered eating has grown, most studies come from North America or Western Europe, leaving Central Europe largely understudied. The Czech Republic offers an important context for extending this work. Central and Eastern European countries, such as the Czech Republic, differ from North America and Western Europe in their post-socialist sociocultural context, including shifts in parenting norms, gender roles, and family stress following rapid political and economic transitions after 1989. At the same time, the region has experienced a substantial rise in adolescents being overweight or obese (Sigmund et al., 2018), reflecting an ongoing epidemiological transition. Examining attachment and eating-related outcomes in this context, therefore, tests whether associations established in Western samples generalize to populations shaped by different historical and structural conditions.

The aim of the present study, based on a large and representative sample of Czech youth, was to examine the relationships between perceived maternal and paternal insecure attachment styles (anxious and avoidant) and three outcomes: food addiction, EDs, and weight status.

The current study

Although studies have demonstrated links between insecure attachment and maladaptive eating behaviours, the focus has predominantly been on children or adults, leaving adolescent-specific relationships underexamined. For example, meta-analyses confirm that food addiction affects adolescents (Skinner et al., 2021), yet few studies assess its association with both maternal and paternal attachment in this age group. Similarly, recent research has identified insecure attachment as a risk factor for EDs in adolescents (Naor-Ziv, 2024), but comprehensive studies examining multiple eating- and weight-related developmental outcomes in the same adolescent sample are missing. Despite evidence that adolescents with eating disorders frequently perceive their fathers as less caring and more controlling, paternal attachment remains markedly understudied (Gander, 2015).

This study addresses these gaps in the literature by exploring the unique and combined or additive effects of adolescent-perceived insecure attachment to both mothers and fathers on food addiction, EDs, and weight status.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the associations between food addiction, obesity, EDs, and attachment in Czech adolescents aged 15–19 years, while also validating Czech versions of key measurement tools. Based on the previous evidence and the general paucity of research linking attachment difficulties and food-related problems among adolescents, the present study tested the following hypotheses.

It was expected that

H1: Both perceived avoidant attachment with mothers or fathers would be positively associated with higher levels of food addiction and eating disorders, as well as increased likelihood of higher weight status (including overweight, obesity).

H2: Both perceived anxious attachment with mothers or fathers would be positively associated with higher levels of food addiction and eating disorders, as well as increased likelihood of higher weight status (including overweight, obesity).

H3: Sex would moderate the relationships between perceived insecure attachment (avoidant and anxious) with mothers and fathers, food addiction, eating disorders, and risk for higher weight status. No directional effects were hypothesized about potential sex differences related to whether the effects would be potentiated (larger) for males versus females.

Method

Participants

Data were collected from $N = 3,677$ adolescents (1,688 boys, 45.9% and 1,989 girls, 54.1%) aged 15–19 years who attended a school in one of the 14 administrative regions of the Czech Republic. The total study population included 398,456 students who were attending ISCED 3 educational level schools, namely four-year grammar schools, high schools with a leaving exam, and high schools without a leaving exam. Stratified sampling was used to select schools from each of the main 14 regions in the Czech Republic within each type of school, and the goal was to recruit at least 2 school types from each region. A random number generator was used to select schools from a list of all schools. School principals were contacted by letter, e-mail, and finally by telephone. The final sample included 39 schools (of a total of 79 schools invited, thus 49.4% of contacted schools agreed to participate). Data collection was carried out between May 2019 and March 2020. Respondents and schools were provided with detailed information regarding the research objectives and outcomes.

Procedures

Adolescents completed an anonymous paper-and-pencil self-report survey in classrooms during a one-hour period. A researcher was present to supervise the data collection and to address questions. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were not compensated for taking part in the study. Researchers strictly followed a standardized research protocol to ensure consistency during data collection. Data were collected following Czech laws and regulations and protecting human subjects, consistent with the Helsinki Convention (2024 Revision) on the protection of human subjects. Such data collections are considered exempt from formal ethics approval and review by the local university ethics review committee when anonymous data are collected from youth who are 15 years or older. Thus, participants 15 years and older provided consent consistent with GDPR Article 8 implementation in the Czech Republic and EU ethical guidance (European Union, 2016; Úřad pro ochranu osobních údajů, 2019; European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, 2014). National and EU-level guidelines affirm that adolescents aged 15 and above are considered capable of providing informed consent independently, particularly in non-interventional and low-risk research settings European Medicines Agency (2015).

Measures

All assessments, including the Eating Disorder Examination Questionnaire—8-item version (EDE-Q8) and Experiences in Close Relationships—Relationship Structures Questionnaire (ECR-RS), were translated into Czech following WHO guidelines for instrument translation and adaptation. This process involved multiple forward translations, back-translations, and expert panel review to ensure conceptual and linguistic equivalence. All instruments subsequently underwent linguistic validation in line with the World Health Organization (WHO) (2020).

Demographics. Student characteristics were collected, including age, sex, family structure, ethnicity, and parental education.

Participants self-reported their height and weight, which were used to calculate BMI. BMI percentiles were categorized based on WHO norms (2007) into underweight, normal weight, overweight, and obese. For analysis, binary variables were created to contrast each category against all others.

Experiences in close relationships-relationship structures questionnaire (ECR-RS). Attachment was measured using the ECR-RS (Fraley et al., 2011), assessing relationship-specific attachment styles toward mothers and fathers. In the original validation study, the ECR-RS demonstrated good convergent validity with the ECR-R and expected associations with relationship functioning and personality traits, supporting its construct validity (Fraley et al., 2011). Participants rated nine items per relationship on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree). Scores were calculated for two dimensions: avoidance (6 items) and anxiety (3 items), separately for each parent. Internal consistency in the current sample was acceptable: maternal avoidance ($\alpha = .87$), maternal anxiety ($\alpha = .81$), paternal avoidance ($\alpha = .85$), and paternal anxiety ($\alpha = .85$).

Modified yale food addiction scale 2.0 (mYFAS 2.0). Food addiction was assessed using 11 items from the Modified Yale Food Addiction Scale 2.0 (Gearhardt et al., 2016), excluding two clinical significance items. Responses were given on an 8-point scale (1 = Never to 8 = Every day), dichotomized and summed into a symptom count score (range: 0–11). Higher scores indicate greater symptoms of food addiction. Internal consistency in this sample was $\alpha = .74$.

A recent study using Rasch analysis showed that the mYFAS 2.0 has good psychometric properties, with no item misfit and a clear one-factor structure. The scale can distinguish between different levels of addictive-like eating, and it performs similarly across gender and BMI groups. These findings support the mYFAS 2.0 as a reliable and valid brief measure of food addiction in young people (Saffari et al., 2022). This version of the scale was previously validated in a Czech population (Pipová et al., 2020).

Eating disorder examination-questionnaire Q8 (EDE-Q8). Disordered eating was measured using the EDE-Q8 (Kliem et al., 2015), a short form assessing ED psychopathology. The EDE-Q8 has demonstrated a unidimensional factor structure, good model fit, high internal consistency ($\alpha \approx .90$), and strong convergent validity with the full EDE-Q (Kliem et al., 2015). Items were rated on scales reflecting symptom frequency or severity over the past 28 days. A total score was computed as the mean of 8 items. Higher scores indicate greater ED pathology. Internal consistency in our sample was $\alpha = .67$. EDE-Q8 was translated into Czech following WHO guidelines for instrument translation and adaptation, including forward translation, back-translation, expert review, and pilot testing. The scale subsequently underwent linguistic validation.

Weight status. Participants were asked to report weight and height, which were used to calculate BMI as the ratio of body weight to the square of body height (WHO, 2000). The calculated BMI values assigned each participant to a weight group based on WHO averages for each adolescent age group (World Health Organization, 2007). The overweight category includes individuals with a BMI value greater than 1 standard deviation for the age and sex of the child, and the obese category includes individuals with a value greater than 2 standard deviations for the age and sex of the child (World Health Organization, 2007). For the purposes of analyzes, BMI dichotomized into four variables used in subsequent analyzes: (1) overweight versus others (overweight and obese versus others), (2) obese versus others (obese versus others), (3) overweight (overweight versus others), and (4) underweight (underweight versus others).

Plan of analysis

Attachment avoidance and anxiety towards mothers and fathers were added as the key focal variables of interest, consistent with the study aims and hypotheses. Additional correlates included in the regression models were selected based on theoretical importance and prior research identifying demographic characteristics (age, sex, ethnicity, family structure, and parental education) as correlates or covariates of adolescent health behaviours as well as eating behaviours in particular.

In an initial step, descriptive statistics were computed, including assessments of internal consistency for the main study constructs. Table 1 includes this information for the total sample. Next, correlations were computed between background variables and the main study constructs, which are shown in Table 2. Finally, a series of hierarchical regression analyzes were tested, which included background variables on an initial step, followed by the global anxiety score as well as the global avoidance score to predict food addiction and eating disorder scores, as well as a logistic regression to predict the BMI risk scores (four

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of background variables and main study constructs.

	<i>n</i>	Mean/%	SD	<i>Alphas</i>	Sex differences F value
Age	3,677	16.79	1.00		
Sex					
Males	1,688	45.9			
Females	1,989	54.1			
Family structure					
Two biological parents	2,544	69.2			
Other	1,133	30.8			
Ethnicity					
Czech	3,274	89.0			
Other	403	11.0			
Maternal education	3,543	3.35	1.20		
Paternal education	3,393	3.24	1.26		
Maternal avoidance	3,286	3.68	1.11	.87	44.22***
Maternal anxiety	3,286	1.68	1.21	.81	31.32***
Paternal avoidance	3,159	4.29	1.08	.85	78.21***
Paternal anxiety	3,159	1.95	1.47	.85	66.78***
Food addiction	3,589	2.54	2.26	.74	207.38***
Eating disorder	3,611	1.37	1.65	.67	142.38***
BMI score	3,552	22.19	3.58		67.24***

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$. FAM = family structure (1 = two biological parents); ethnicity (1 = ethnic Czech youth, 0 = other).

Table 2. Correlations among main study constructs.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1. Age													
2. Sex (1 = male)	-.03												
3. Family structure	-.06**	-.03											
4. Maternal education	-.05**	-.04*	.10**										
5. Paternal education	-.02	-.03	.11**	.50**									
6. Ethnicity	.01	.02	.07**	.04**	.03								
7. Maternal avoidance	.03	-.08**	-.09**	-.05*	.00	-.04*							
8. Maternal anxiety	-.01	.10**	-.12**	-.11**	-.05*	-.05**	.38**						
9. Paternal avoidance	.00	.13**	-.21**	-.06**	-.06**	-.06**	.34**	.18**					
10. Paternal anxiety	.00	.14**	-.26**	-.10**	-.09**	-.08**	.12**	.50**	.45**				
11. Food addiction	.00	.23**	-.01	.03	.02	-.01	.14**	.20**	.18**	.18**			
12. Eating disorder	.03	.19**	-.06**	-.02	-.03	-.03	.13**	.15**	.16**	.14**	.57**		
13. BMI2	-.01	-.09**	-.06**	-.09**	-.07**	-.04*	.04*	.06**	.04*	.05**	.03	.11*	
14. BMI3	.00	-.10**	-.02	-.04*	-.07**	-.02	.04*	.02	.00	.03	.06**	.15**	-.10**

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$. FAM = family structure (1 = two biological parents); ethnicity (1 = ethnic Czech youth, 0 = other); BMI2 = obese (1 = obese youth, 0 = other); BMI3 = overweight (overweight youth, 0 = other).

dichotomous measures of BMI). All regression models report unstandardized coefficients, p -values, and 95% confidence intervals. All analyzes were carried out in IBM SPSS 29, with missing values treated using pairwise deletion; no additional method was employed to address missing data.

Results

In an initial step, descriptive statistics were computed on background variables as well as the main study constructs. Table 1 includes frequencies as well as means of these variables, along with reliability estimates of the focal variables all of which were acceptable (maternal avoidance $\alpha = .87$; maternal anxiety $\alpha = .81$; paternal avoidance $\alpha = .85$; paternal anxiety $\alpha = .85$; food addiction $\alpha = .74$; eating disorder $\alpha = .67$). The table also reports sex differences for all focal variables, including parental attachment, food addiction, eating disorder symptoms, and weight-status categories. Statistically significant mean level differences were found by sex across all of these measures, where girls reported higher scores, with the exception of the BMI score, where boys scored higher (maternal avoidance: $F = 44.22$, $p < .001$; maternal anxiety: $F = 31.32$, $p < .001$; paternal avoidance: $F = 78.21$, $p < .001$; paternal anxiety: $F = 66.78$, $p < .001$; food addiction: $F = 207.38$, $p < .001$; eating disorder: $F = 142.38$, $p < .001$; BMI score: $F = 67.24$, $p < .001$). Table 3 presents BMI information for the total sample as well as for boys versus girls, broken down into the four main categories, namely underweight, normal, overweight, and obese.

Next, Pearson's correlations were computed among the study variables which are included in Table 2. Girls scored higher on food addiction ($r = .23$, $p < .01$) and eating disorder symptoms ($r = .19$, $p < .01$), while

Table 3. Frequencies of BMI categories (total sample and by sex).

	Total sample <i>n</i> (%)		Boys (<i>n</i> = 1,627) <i>n</i> (%)		Girls (<i>n</i> = 1,925) <i>n</i> (%)	
Underweight	59	1.7%	21	1.3%	38	2.0%
Normal weight	2,758	77.6%	1,174	72.2%	1,584	82.3%
Overweight	560	15.8%	318	19.5%	242	12.6%
Obese	175	4.9%	114	7.0%	61	3.2%

Table 4. Regression models predicting food addiction.

Step	Variable	<i>b</i>	SE <i>B</i>	β	<i>p</i>	95% CI
Step 1	Age	0.27	0.04	0.01	.503	−0.05 to 0.11
	Sex (1 = male)	1.07	0.08	0.24***	<.001	0.91 to 1.23
	Maternal education	0.03	0.04	0.02	.406	−0.05 to 0.11
	Paternal education	0.04	0.04	0.02	.314	−0.04 to 0.12
	Family structure	−0.08	0.10	−0.02	.395	−0.27 to 0.11
Step 2	Ethnicity	−0.02	0.14	−0.00	.908	−0.29 to 0.25
	Age	0.03	0.04	0.01	.400	−0.05 to 0.11
	Sex (1 = male)	0.98	0.08	0.22***	<.001	0.83 to 1.13
	Maternal education	0.07	0.04	0.04	.066	−0.05 to 0.15
	Paternal education	−0.03	0.04	0.02	.314	−0.12 to 0.04
	Family structure	0.15	0.10	0.03	.122	−0.04 to 0.34
	Ethnicity	0.07	0.14	0.01	.592	−0.20 to 0.34
	Maternal avoidance	0.14	0.03	0.09***	<.001	0.07 to 0.2
	Maternal anxiety	0.23	0.05	0.12***	<.001	0.11 to 0.26
	Paternal avoidance	0.14	0.03	0.09***	<.001	0.05 to 0.19
Paternal anxiety	0.07	0.04	0.05	.089	−0.03 to 0.43	

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$. Family structure (1 = two biological parents); ethnicity (1 = ethnic Czech youth, 0 = other).

boys showed higher rates of overweight ($r = -.10$, $p < .01$) and obesity ($r = -.09$, $p < .01$). Boys had higher rates of overweight (19.5%) and obesity (7.0%) compared to girls (12.6% and 3.2%, respectively). Girls had a slightly higher prevalence of underweight (2.0%) compared to boys (1.3%). Age was not related to the dependent measures (food addiction: $r = .00$, ns; eating disorder: $r = .03$, ns; obesity: $r = -.01$, ns; overweight: $r = .00$, ns). Related to the study hypotheses and the main research questions, the perceived maternal as well as paternal avoidance and anxiety scores were positively associated with food addiction (maternal avoidance: $r = .14$, $p < .01$; maternal anxiety: $r = .20$, $p < .01$; paternal avoidance: $r = .18$, $p < .01$; paternal anxiety: $r = .18$, $p < .01$) as well as eating disorders (maternal avoidance: $r = .13$, $p < .01$; maternal anxiety: $r = .15$, $p < .01$; paternal avoidance: $r = .16$, $p < .01$; paternal anxiety: $r = .14$, $p < .01$), but to a much lesser extent for obesity and being overweight.

Complete model estimates, including p -values and 95% confidence intervals, are presented in Tables 4–6. Two sets of regression analyzes were carried out. The first one focused on both food addictions as well as eating disorders; results are shown in Tables 4 and 5. A hierarchical regression was carried out, where on the first step background variables were added to the model, while on the second step both the perceived maternal as well as paternal scores of avoidance and anxiety were added to the regression. Consistent with study hypotheses, the perceived maternal avoidance (food addiction: $b = 0.14$, $SE = 0.03$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.07, 0.20]; eating disorder: $b = 0.10$, $SE = 0.03$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.06, 0.16]), the perceived maternal anxiety (food addiction: $b = 0.23$, $SE = 0.05$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.11, 0.26]; eating disorder: $b = 0.11$, $SE = 0.03$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.03, 0.14]), as well as the perceived paternal avoidance (food addiction: $b = 0.14$, $SE = 0.03$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.05, 0.19]; eating disorder: $b = 0.08$, $SE = 0.03$, $p = .003$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.11]) each significantly predicted both food addiction as well as eating disorders. The only consistent background variable that reached statistical significance was sex (food addiction: $b = 0.98$, $SE = 0.08$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.83, 1.13]; eating disorder: $b = 0.61$, $SE = 0.06$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.48, 0.72]).

The second set of analyzes were logistic regressions that focused on two dichotomous BMI scores, coded for being obese as well as coded for being overweight. Results from these analyzes are summarized in Table 6. Contrary to expectations, only sex ($b = -0.94$, $SE = 0.20$, $OR = 0.39$, 95% CI [0.262, 0.565], $p < .001$) as well as maternal education ($b = -0.41$, $SE = 0.10$, $OR = 0.66$, 95% CI [0.553, 0.809], $p < .001$) emerged as significant correlates for being obese, whereas sex ($b = -0.56$, $SE = 0.11$, $OR = 0.57$, 95% CI [0.462, 0.708], $p < .001$) and paternal educational level ($b = -0.15$, $SE = 0.05$, $OR = 0.86$, 95% CI [0.779, 0.941], $p < .001$) were found to be significant predictors of obesity or overweight status based on the BMI score (all $ps > .05$).

Table 5. Regression models predicting eating disorder.

Step	Variable	b	SE B	β	<i>p</i>	95% CI
Step 1	Age	0.04	0.03	0.02	.256	−0.03 to 0.09
	Sex (1 = male)	0.65	0.06	0.20***	<.001	0.53 to 0.77
	Maternal education	0.00	0.03	0.00	.997	−0.06 to 0.06
	Paternal education	−0.02	0.03	−0.01	.555	−0.07 to 0.03
	Family structure	−0.19	0.07	−0.05**	.008	−0.33 to −0.05
	Ethnicity	−0.12	0.10	−0.02	.234	−0.33 to 0.08
Step 2	Age	0.03	0.03	0.02	.269	−0.03 to 0.09
	Sex (1 = male)	0.61	0.06	0.18***	<.001	0.48 to 0.72
	Maternal education	0.02	0.03	0.02	.440	−0.03 to 0.08
	Paternal education	−0.02	0.03	−0.02	.432	−0.07 to 0.03
	Family structure	−0.06	0.07	−0.02	.479	−0.19 to 0.09
	Ethnicity	−0.08	0.10	−0.01	.432	−0.28 to 0.12
	Maternal avoidance	0.10	0.03	0.09***	<.001	0.06 to 0.16
	Maternal anxiety	0.11	0.03	0.08***	<.001	0.03 to 0.14
	Paternal avoidance	0.08	0.03	0.07**	.003	0.01 to 0.11
	Paternal anxiety	0.03	0.03	0.03	.032	0.01 to 0.11

Note: **p* < .05, ***p* < .01, ****p* < .001. Family structure (1 = two biological parents); ethnicity (1 = ethnic Czech youth, 0 = other).

Table 6. Logistic regressions predicting BMI groups (obese and overweight).

Predictor	Obesity				Overweight			
	b	SE	OR	95% CI	b	SE	OR	95% CI
Age	−0.01	0.09	0.99	0.829 to 1.190	−0.52	0.05	0.95	0.855 to 1.053
Sex (1 = male)	−0.94***	0.20	0.39	0.262 to 0.565	−0.56***	0.11	0.57	0.462 to 0.708
Maternal education	−0.41***	0.10	0.66	0.553 to 0.809	0.20	0.05	1.02	0.924 to 1.127
Paternal education	−0.04	0.09	0.64	0.808 to 1.134	−0.15***	0.05	0.86	0.779 to 0.941
Family structure	−0.46	0.10	0.63	0.433 to 0.950	−0.70	0.12	0.93	0.729 to 1.183
Ethnicity	−0.43	0.26	0.65	0.389 to 1.091	−0.11	0.17	0.89	0.635 to 1.245
Maternal avoidance	−0.04	0.07	0.96	0.824 to 1.113	0.04	0.04	1.04	0.958 to 1.144
Maternal anxiety	0.12	0.09	1.13	0.960 to 1.306	−0.03	0.06	0.97	0.880 to 1.077
Paternal avoidance	0.09	0.08	1.10	0.932 to 1.268	−0.03	0.05	0.97	0.878 to 1.052
Paternal anxiety	−0.06	0.08	0.99	0.985 to 1.174	0.07	0.05	1.08	0.985 to 1.174
Cox & Snell/Nagelkerke R ²	.023/.016				.023/.027			

Discussion

The present study tested whether insecure attachment to both mothers and fathers is associated with food-related problems, operationalized as food addiction and EDs, as well as with weight-related indicators, such as higher weight status. Boys reported higher rates of obesity (7.0% vs. 3.2%) and being overweight (19.5% vs. 12.6%) than girls. Hypothesis 1 was partially supported, showing that the perceived maternal and parental avoidance was positively linked to food addiction and eating disorders. However, neither construct was associated with higher weight status, being obese or overweight. Secondly, Hypothesis 2 was also partially supported; perceived maternal anxiety was associated with food addiction and ED risk, but not with higher weight status. Unexpectedly, paternal anxiety scores were unrelated to all four dependent measures. Maternal and paternal avoidance, along with the perceived maternal anxiety, showed modest associations with food addiction and EDs and, again, were unrelated to either obesity or being overweight, thus not supporting Hypothesis 3. The study's findings are largely consistent with the existing literature, highlighting the relationship between perceived parental insecure attachment styles and food-related challenges among adolescents. Consistent with previous research on attachment and eating pathology in adolescence, perceived maternal and paternal avoidance emerged as modest but consistent correlates of both food addiction and ED risk (Jewell et al., 2023).

Sex differences were also evident in the present sample. Girls comprised 54.1% of the participants and reported significantly higher levels of food addiction ($b = 0.98$, $SE = 0.08$, $p < .001$) and eating-disorder symptoms ($b = 0.61$, $SE = 0.06$, $p < .001$), whereas boys showed higher odds of obesity ($OR = 0.39$, 95% CI [0.262–0.565]) and overweight status ($OR = 0.57$, 95% CI [0.462–0.708]). These findings suggest important sex differences in the risk for food addiction as well as obesity or overweight status and highlight the relevance of sex distribution when interpreting eating-related outcomes in adolescent samples.

Research on food addiction and attachment is limited. In a study of the adult population, Pipová et al. (2020) found that participants who had insecure attachment styles exhibited elevated YFAS scores. Troisi et al. (2005) suggested that food, especially comfort food, can provide temporary relief from the anxiety resulting from insecure attachments. Takgbajouah and Buscemi (2022) proposed the theory of Hedonic

Hunger (HH), where eating for pleasure mirrors binge eating and substance use, suggesting that food addiction (FA) may share similar roots. Negative childhood experiences, linked to insecure attachment and emotional dysregulation, are associated with compulsive behaviours such as substance use and maladaptive eating, including FA. Bartholomew and Horowitz (1991) explained that those with avoidant attachments often distance themselves from emotional intimacy, neglecting their need for closeness. Food can then act as a substitute for unmet emotional needs. This emotional distancing can lead to maladaptive coping mechanisms, such as seeking solace in food, to manage or numb feelings (Mauder & Hunter, 2001). Moreover, the internalized neglect stemming from perceived parental neglect might manifest as self-neglect in adulthood, potentially contributing to disordered eating (Mikulincer & Shaver, 2019). Mikulincer and Shaver (2003) explained that attachment, particularly with mothers, can make adolescents more likely to have food issues. This is because those with anxiety in relationships often seek closeness and approval, which can lead to emotional eating when they feel relationship stress. Zawertailo et al. (2020) highlighted similarities between food addiction and substance use disorders, particularly tobacco use, toing shared factors like childhood adversity, and attachment insecurity.

Regarding EDs, study findings are largely consistent with previous evidence on the link between insecure attachment and disordered eating. Abbate-Daga et al. (2010) found that patients with an ED diagnosis, regardless of type, had insecure attachment styles; this link was also noted by Zachrisson and Skårderud (2010). Orzolek-Kronner (2002) proposed that EDs might stem from repeated proximity-seeking behaviours, while Ringer and Crittenden (2007) suggested that hidden family conflict in the relationship of parents, as well as their histories of trauma, contribute to the development of insecure attachment patterns and EDs. Eggert et al. (2007) have proposed that the relationships between attachment style and disordered eating are indirect, in that neuroticism might mediate the insecure-resistant attachment and disordered eating link. In clinical samples, there is a strong association between insecure attachment and EDs ($r = 0.41$) (Caglar-Nazali et al., 2014). Insecure attachment styles are significantly more prevalent among individuals with EDs compared to controls. Higher attachment insecurity also correlates with unhealthy eating behaviours in general population samples (e.g. Faber et al., 2018). Finally, Tasca et al. (2006) hypothesized that attachment influences affect regulation strategies, which in turn influence EDs.

Study findings highlight the importance of father-adolescent relationships, particularly avoidant attachment, for both food addiction and EDs (Rohner & Veneziano, 2001); furthermore, Gutzwiller et al. (2003) emphasizes the significant role of fathers during middle adolescence in relation to EDs. Regarding the link between higher weight status and attachment, Diener et al. (2016) found that insecure attachment is associated with lower body mass index (BMI) in adults. Insecure attachment style was associated with higher BMI. Diener et al. (2016) meta-analysis provided evidence that secure attachment is associated with lower BMI for adults. For children, the same link was found, although the findings were not conclusive. In fact, Maras et al. (2016) found insecure attachment positively linked to BMI, mediated by restrained eating. Kim (2019) suggests that while there are no direct links between early attachment or parental stress and obesity risk during adolescence, child self-regulation emerges as a key factor. Specifically, it mediates the relationship between early attachment and both adverse dietary choices and the potential for obesity during the teenage years. Additionally, a child's BMI during their early years is seen to indirectly influence their BMI in adolescence (Kim, 2019).

The logistic regression analyzes provided evidence linking parental educational attainment with risk for being obese or overweight. These findings are consistent with those made in the United States, where Singh et al. (2008) found that lower parental education was associated with higher rates of childhood obesity. Children whose parents had less than 12 years of education were more than twice as likely to be obese as those with parents who had more than 12 years of education. Wang and Lim (2012) explain that parents' education, along with income and occupation, contribute to SES. Generally, in developed countries, lower SES is often associated with higher obesity rates; however, in some developing nations, higher SES might mean more childhood obesity. Park et al. (2014) noted that higher education is often linked to better nutrition knowledge, healthier food choices, and balanced meals. Educated parents may limit junk food and prioritize nutrition. Education also correlates with better economic status, enabling access to healthier foods, gyms, and safer recreational areas (Drewnowski & Almiron-Roig, 2010). On the other hand, Shrewsbury and Wardle (2008) discuss that while many studies underscore the relationship between parents' education and childhood obesity, some studies might find no significant relationship or might find that other factors (like parental weight status, cultural practices, etc.) play a more substantial role. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2020) recently noted that while parents' education has

been identified as a factor in childhood obesity in the U.S., many studies have shown that the relationship is multifactorial, with variables like household income, neighbourhood safety, and access to fresh foods also playing critical roles. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (2020) also highlights factors such as neighbourhoods, access to healthy food options, and health care services that influence obesity risk.

The study had several limitations. First, its cross-sectional design is purely correlational and cannot establish causality. Experimental and longitudinal studies could provide deeper insights into the developmental importance of these findings and whether the link between attachment styles and food problems is stable or changes over time. Second, while the sample included Czech adolescents from all 13 regions, it was a convenience sample, not randomly selected. Third, reliance on adolescent self-reports may introduce monomethod biases, which future studies could address by including additional reporters. Moreover, the current self-report instruments were not used for clinical diagnoses; thus, study findings reflect perceived symptomatology rather than objectively verified ones of eating disorders.

It is also important to note that due to the absence of measuring general psychopathology, the present study findings need to be interpreted with this limitation in mind. More specifically, it is certainly possible that once a measure of depression was added to model tests, for instance, the observed relationships between attachment insecurity and measures of food addiction and EDs might have been diminished or even eliminated. Future work needs to test the same models incorporating a measure of general psychopathology to rule out this potential threat to the present study's conclusions (see, e.g. Jewell et al., 2023). The relatively low alpha coefficient of .67 for the EDEQ8 needs to be considered when interpreting the present study findings; it also indicates that the observed relationships in the current investigation might in fact have been attenuated.

Conclusion

This study shows that maternal avoidance, maternal anxiety, and paternal avoidance are linked to a higher risk of food addiction and eating disorder symptoms in adolescents, above and beyond known correlates and background variables. These findings underline the key role of the quality of parent–adolescent relationships in understanding and explaining variability in adolescent eating behaviours or problems, thus identifying parent- or family-focused approaches as promising targets for prevention and early intervention efforts. Although boys and girls differed in the mean levels of food addiction, eating disorder symptoms, and BMI categories, the associations between insecure attachment and eating-related outcomes were observed in the total sample and were not found to differ by sex.

Author contributions

Helena Pipová—data curation, investigation, writing—original draft. Martin Dolejš—data curation, investigation, supervision. Jaroslava Suchá—data curation, methodology, investigation. Alexander T. Vazsonyi—conceptualization, formal analysis, supervision, validation, writing—review and editing.

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Data availability statement

Data are available upon request from the first author.

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